

Ethnomedicinal plants used for body cooling by the Primitive and Vulnerable tribal Groups (PVTG's) of Visakhapatnam Dt., Andhra Pradesh

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Received: July 09, 2025

Accepted: July 31, 2025

Published: Aug 05, 2025

Abstract: The present study denotes the documentation of 18 ethnomedicinal plants used for body cooling by the primitive and vulnerable tribal groups (PVTG's) of Visakhapatnam district, Andhra Pradesh. *Malaxis rheedii*, *Vitis heyneana* and 6 practices were found to be new or less known.

Key words: Ethnomedicine, Body cooling, Primitive and Vulnerable Tribals, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh.

I. Introduction

Visakhapatnam district is one of the north eastern coastal districts of Andhra Pradesh. The study area lies between 17°-34' 11" and 18°-32' 57" northern latitude and 18°-51' 49" and 83°-16' 9" in eastern longitude. It is bounded on the north partly by Orissa state and partly by Vizianagaram district, on south by East Godavari district, on west by Orissa state and east by Bay of Bengal with 43 mandals, of which 11 (Chintapalli, Koyyuru, G.K.Veedhi, G.Madugula, Paderu, Pedabayalu, Munchingiputtu, Hukumpeta, Dumbriguda, Araku valley and Ananthagiri) are situated in the hilly areas known as the agency area. The entire agency track covers 6, 298 Km² i. e., 56.4% of the total geographical area of the district. The total population of Andhra Pradesh according to 2001 census is 76,210,007 of which tribals constitute 5, 024,104 accounting for 6.59% of the total population. The total population of Visakhapatnam district is 3,832,336 of which the tribals are 557, 572 (14.55%). The primitive tribal groups constitute 126,778 (3.30%). The scheduled areas extend over 31,485.34 Km² which is about 11% of total area of the state with 5,938 villages. There are 35 ST communities living in the state of which 12 belongs to PTGs. There are 11 tribal communities in the study area and four of them are of Primitive Tribal Group viz., Gadaba, Khond, Porja and Savara. Though there are publications on ethnomedicine for various diseases on PVTGs exclusive publications on body cooling were not present necessitating the present study (Ganesan et.al. 2005, Katewa and Galav 2005, Kumar et.al. 2008, Reddy et.al. 2008, Uddin et.al. 2019).

II. Material and Methods

The ethnobotanical survey was conducted during 2008-2012 covering the eleven mandals of the study area and interviews were conducted with the tribes at their habitats. During oral interviews with elder people, medicine men in the tribal area collected first hand ethnomedicinal uses, mode of preparation and administration of medicine. Each medicinal practice was cross checked with at least 3-4 informants. During field survey information was gathered on plants used for various ailments. In 95 pockets of the study area, 139 *vaidhyas* and practitioners were consulted. The specimens were identified with the help of standard floras (Gamble, 1915-1935 and Rao and Kumari, 2008). The voucher specimens were deposited in the Herbarium of the Department of Botany, *Andhra University*, Visakhapatnam.

III. Enumeration

The plants are arranged in an alphabetical order with botanical name followed by family, vernacular name (VN), English name (E), location (L), method, mode and duration of the treatment. Plants and practices marked with an asterisk (*) are considered to be new or less known.

Aegle marmelos (L.) Correa in Trans. (Rutaceae) VN: Maredu

Two spoonful of fruit paste mixed in a glass of buttermilk administered daily once for three days.

Aloe vera (L.) Burm. f. (Liliaceae) VN: Kala bandha, E: Common Indian aloe,
L: Nadam veedhi, (Hukumpeta)

20 g of mucilaginous jelly from leaves is eaten twice a day for 2 days.

Argyreia nervosa (Burm. f.) Boj. (Convolvulaceae) VN: Gumada mada, E: Elephant creeper,
L: Bonampalli (GK Veedhi)

*Root paste is administered with half tea glass of water once a day.

Blumea axillaris (Lam.) DC. (Asteraceae) VN: Kukka pugaku

Leaf paste used for cooling effect

Caryota urens L. (Arecaceae) VN: Jeeluga, E: Fish tail palm, L: Korapalli (G.Madugula)

Toddy is taken in limited to control body pains and to cool the body.

Cocculus hirsutus (L.) Diels (Menispermaceae) VN: Dusara teega, E: Broom creeper

L: Bayalukinchengi (Chintapalli)

A spoonful of leaf paste mixed in a glass of hot milk is administered daily once for a week.

Costus speciosus (Koen.) Smith (Zingiberaceae) VN: Sengalva kostu, E: Spiral ginger, L: Edulagaruvu (Hukumpeta)

Tuber paste is applied all over the body.

Curcuma pseudomontana Graham, Cat. (Zingiberaceae) VN: Adavi pasupu

Rhizome paste with a pinch of cheese applied on the head for one hour daily once for two days.

Drymaria cordata (L.) Willd. ex Roem. & Schult. (Caryophyllaceae) VN: Ankidukki osso, L: Thotalagondi (G. Madugula)

Fifty g of leaf paste is administered with half tea glass of water twice a day for 2 days.

Ficus benghalensis L. (Moraceae) VN: Marri, E: Banyan tree, L: Bakuru (Hukumpeta)

*2 drops of leaf latex mixed with a spoonful of turmeric in a glass of water is administered thrice a day.

Globba marantina L. (Zingiberaceae) VN: Konda pasupu, L: Thotalagondi (G. Madugula)

*Tuber paste mixed with coconut oil is applied all over the body at the time of fever.

Kaempferia glanga L. (Zingiberaceae) VN: Kasturidumpa, L: Modapalli (Paderu)

Tuber paste mixed with half tea glass of water is administered twice for one day only.

****Malaxis rheedii*** Sw. (Orchidaceae) VN: Saluva mandu, L: Kusumagaruvu (Pedabayalu)

Tuberous paste is applied all over the body during fever.

Martynia annua L. (Martyniaceae) VN: Thelukondi, E: Tiger's claw, L: Chaparathipalem, (G.K. Veedhi)

*Leaf paste is applied on the scalp for one hour before head bath.

Phyllanthus emblica L. (Euphorbiaceae) VN: Pedda usiri

A spoonful of juice of tender fruits and flowers administered daily twice for three days.

Vetiveria zizanioides (L.) Nash in Small, (Poaceae) VN: Vatti veru

Leaf oil applied on the scalp daily twice for three days

****Vitis heyneana*** Roem. & Schultes (Vitaceae) VN: Mediki dumpa, L: Thotalagondi (G. Madugula)

Tubers paste applied all over the body at the time of fever.

Ziziphus mauritiana Lam. (Rhamnaceae) VN: Regu

Fruit paste applied on the scalp for half an hour twice a week.

IV. Discussion and conclusion

The paper deals with 18 plant species as many as genera and families used as body cooling by the PVTG's of Visakhapatnam district, Andhra Pradesh. Habit-wise analysis showed the dominance of herbs with 7 species followed by climber 3 species and trees 2 species. Morphological analysis showed the maximum utilization of leaf and tuber in 5 practices each followed by root and inflorescence (1 each). *Malaxis rheedii*, *Vitis heyneana* and 6 practices are found to be new or less known (Jain 1991, Kirtikar and Basu 2003).

There is an urgent need for follow-up ethnopharmacological screening based on tribal claims and beliefs and formulate and standardize some herbal medicines based on ethnotherapeutics either with single plant or in combination for their safe and sustained use for human welfare.

V. Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the Primitive and vulnerable tribal groups of Visakhapatnam district for sharing their valuable knowledge on ethnomedicine and help during field work.

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